

THE ROLE OF TECHNOLOGY IN TEACHING LISTENING

Teshaboyeva Nafisa Zubaydulla qizi

Jizzakh Branch of the National

University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulug'bek

The faculty of Psychology, department of Foreign languages

Phylology and foreign languages

Ollayorova Mahfuza

Student of group 102-23

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Annotation. Listening skill is always of great significance in language acquisition of all times. It becomes more interactive and productive process via technology in today's modern world. In this article, the author describes some technological tools that aim to help accelerate and ease language learning and listening comprehension ability.

Key words: listening capability, lectures, audios, internet, multimedia, sounds, computer systems.

Аннотация. Навык аудирования всегда имел большое значение в освоении языка во все времена. Он становится более интерактивным и продуктивным процессом благодаря технологиям в современном мире. В этой статье автор описывает некоторые технологические инструменты, которые направлены на ускорение и облегчение изучения языка и способности аудирования.

Ключевые слова: способность аудирования, лекции, аудио, интернет, мультимедиа, звуки, компьютерные системы.

Introduction

Listening is the language modality that is used most frequently. It has been estimated that adults spend almost half their communication time listening, and students may receive as much as 90 % of their in-school information through listening to instructors and to one another. Often, however, language learners do not recognize the level of effort that goes into developing listening ability. Far from passively receiving and recording aural input, listeners actively involve themselves in the interpretation of what they hear, bringing their own background knowledge and linguistic knowledge to bear on the information contained in the aural text. Not all listening is the same; casual greetings, for example, require a different sort of listening capability than do academic lectures. Language learning requires intentional listening that employs strategies for identifying sounds and making meaning from them.

Given the importance of listening in language learning and teaching, it is essential for language teachers to help their students become effective listeners. In the communicative approach to language teaching, this means modeling listening strategies and providing listening practice in authentic situations: those that learners are likely to encounter when they use the language outside the classroom.

The one of the best ways introduce students to listening strategies is to integrate listening activities into language lessons using multimedia technology. As multimedia technology (interactive videodisc, CD-ROM, CD-I, etc.) becomes more accessible to teachers and learners of other languages, its potential as a tool to enhance listening skills becomes a practical option. Multimedia allows integration of text, graphics, audio, and motion video in a range of

combinations. The result is that learners can now interact with textual, aural, and visual media in a wide range of formats.

In addition, listening skills fall into three categories: Passive listening (listening for pleasure or entertainment); Active listening (listening to learn and retain information); and Critical/Analytical listening (listening to critique or make judgments about what one has heard). Modern, computer-based technology fosters listening skills by providing a multitude of opportunities for listening to spoken language. A good language teacher will be aware of these current and emerging technologies to immerse their students in the spoken language experience.

The Internet is suitable place to practise languages as it offers the possibility, with the right software, of using images and audio resources at the same time, combining sounds and images as in communicative situations in the real world. It also provides users with a highly appealing and innovative format. But only when the sources are properly selected can the internet be useful in learning environment. There is a plethora of educational video and audio material available online and accessible via Web search engines such as Google.com.

As an alternative, internet TVs and radios can be used to develop listening comprehension skills of a student in an entertaining atmosphere; however, there is a relatively new emerging phenomenon: YouTube.com! This is a video upload-watch-download site and is increasing its popularity day by day. According to statistics, the site has more than six million videos and the total time necessary to watch all these videos is 9.305 years! This huge video pool offers priceless opportunities to practice listening in an entertaining and convenient environment. Television/radio shows, news, documentaries, music videos and any videos beyond the imagination of people are just one click away. All you need is an internet connection. The rest is almost totally free; however, videos should be carefully selected and prepared by the instructor to maximize comprehension and minimize frustration of learners and they hope that improvement in search tools for videos will allow the teachers to find the right video clip for supporting language class. As BBC has always been seen as a genuine source of “right” form of English, it cannot be disregarded for English Language Teaching. Being aware of its educative role, BBC has been publishing books, audio/video materials and so on.

Apart from that, songs can be highly useful for developmental process of listening skills of a student. As music is everywhere in human life to change or boost the emotions and feelings, we can include music and songs in language learning as well. Besides, karaoke is also beneficial in that it requires a recitation which eventually leads to improvement in speaking skill. Lastly, computer aided games can also have striking effects on student's listening comprehension. Games are proved to be useful during their language education process. When games' attractiveness unites with convenience and flexibility of computers systems, it may cause positive results as well.

Technology has revolutionized the teaching of listening skills in language education by offering diverse tools, resources, and methodologies. Below are more detailed perspectives on its impact:

1. Varied Types of Listening Activities

Audio and Video Materials: Platforms like YouTube, TED Talks, and language learning apps provide authentic audio and video materials that expose students to real-life language usage. These include news, interviews, dialogues, or even entertainment.

Interactive Listening Games: Tools like Kahoot or Quizlet allow teachers to design games where students listen and respond, making learning engaging.

2. Multimodal Learning Approaches

Technology combines listening with other skills (reading, speaking, and writing), fostering multimodal learning:

Subtitles and Transcripts: Many tools include captions that help learners understand context while listening. For instance, Netflix offers multilingual subtitles for language practice.

Speech-to-Text Software: Tools like Otter.ai allow learners to follow along with transcripts as they listen.

3. Adaptive Learning Systems

Modern platforms such as AI-powered apps (e.g., Duolingo, LingQ) adapt to learners' abilities by analyzing their performance and providing customized listening exercises.

Algorithms adjust speech speed, difficulty level, or vocabulary complexity to suit individual learners.

4. Focus on Real-World Listening Contexts

Virtual Reality (VR): VR apps, like Mondly VR, simulate real-world environments, such as airports or restaurants, where learners must listen and respond.

Augmented Reality (AR): Apps overlay auditory information onto physical spaces, making listening contextual and interactive.

5. Gamification to Increase Engagement

Gamified platforms make listening practice enjoyable. For example:

English Listening and Speaking Games: Apps like ELSA Speak incorporate listening activities with immediate rewards to sustain motivation.

6. Feedback and Performance Tracking

Automated Feedback: Many platforms offer real-time feedback on comprehension exercises.

Pronunciation Assessment: Apps like Speechling use voice analysis to assess learners' pronunciation, encouraging active listening

7. Enhancing Teacher-Led Instruction

Teachers use technology to create diverse lesson plans, incorporating podcasts, audiobooks, and online exercises.

Tools like Google Classroom or Edmodo facilitate sharing listening tasks, tracking progress, and engaging in discussions.

8. Collaborative and Social Learning

Language exchange apps (e.g., Tandem, HelloTalk) connect learners with native speakers for authentic listening practice.

Online classrooms allow group listening exercises and discussions, enabling students to learn collaboratively.

9. Accessibility for Diverse Learners

Technology supports students with disabilities through features like adjustable playback speed, closed captions, and specialized tools such as Visual Sound.

It also aids those in remote areas or without access to native speakers by providing online resources.

10. Exposure to Cultural Nuances

Audio and video resources often incorporate cultural elements, helping learners understand idiomatic expressions, humor, and regional accents.

Tools and Platforms for Teaching Listening

Podcasts: (e.g., BBC Learning English, Spotify) offer free listening resources for all proficiency levels.

Streaming Services: Platforms like Netflix or Hulu provide exposure to real-world language.

Dedicated Apps: Tools like Pimsleur, Babbel, or FluentU focus on auditory learning.

Challenges in Using Technology for Listening Instruction

Digital Divide: Not all students have access to necessary devices or stable internet.

Overreliance on Technology: Teachers may neglect traditional methods, leading to potential gaps in skill development.

Technical Difficulties: Issues like poor audio quality or platform bugs can hinder learning.

Content Moderation: Ensuring listening materials are level-appropriate and culturally sensitive.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we may say that using technology in the classroom

- allows teachers to add multisensory elements, text, sound, pictures, video, and animation, which provide meaningful contexts to facilitate comprehension
- allows teachers to increase authentic materials for study
- encourages greater interaction between teachers and students and students and peers
- emphasizes the individual needs of learners
- allows learners to hear the available input as many times as needed until they feel they understand it
- allows learners to develop their autonomy to review and practice materials as many times as they wish
- allows to reduce the learning stresses and anxieties
- allows learners to build their self-instruction strategies and self-confidence
- promotes second language learners' learning motivation.

However, there are disadvantages and obstacles in using technology for improving listening skills in terms of financial barriers, content considerations, technical features and pedagogical perspectives.

There is no doubt that technology offers teachers and learners vast amount of materials and communication possibilities to enhance their language teaching and learning. For successful integration of multimedia technology in language courses, both teachers and learners need to be prepared to adopt new roles and use the available technology in appropriate ways. Teachers should be prepared with professional skills which include pedagogical and technical skill because the more enthusiastic and more knowledgeable language teachers are, the more successfully they can implement Internet in the language classroom. Learners can only benefit from technology – based activities provided that these activities are relevant to their needs and interest.

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